

Predicting College Placements Using XGBoost Classifier

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Abstract— In response to the increasing need for data-driven methods in education, this research explores the application of the XGBoost classifier in college placement prediction. The research uses data preparation techniques to manage missing values and encode categorical variables. It does this by utilizing a dataset from college placement records that includes important parameters like age, gender, academic achievement, and internships. After that, the produced dataset is used to train and assess the XGBoost classifier, which shows encouraging accuracy in placement prediction. These results demonstrate how machine learning may improve placement tactics, help students make wise career decisions, and maximize academic results.

Keywords— XGBoost Classifier, College Placements, Predictive Modeling, Machine Learning

I. INTRODUCTION

The education sector is witnessing a significant transformation with the integration of data-driven technologies. Using machine learning algorithms for predictive analysis in educational contexts is one such use. Predicting college placements in particular is extremely important to both students and educational institutions. Precise prediction of student placements helps universities to maximize their placement tactics, and it also empowers students to make knowledgeable judgments about their future careers.

College placement is a complex process that is impacted by a wide range of variables, such as extracurricular activity participation, academic achievement, student demographics, and industry demand. Placement selections have often been determined using a combination of limited data analysis, intuition, and historical tendencies. But the emergence of machine learning has opened up new avenues, enabling organizations to use data to make more objective and well-informed placement decisions.

Due to their strong performance in classification problems, ensemble learning algorithms such as XGBoost have become more and more popular in recent years. These

algorithms work effectively for forecasting college placements because they can handle large, complicated datasets with high-dimensional features. XGBoost can efficiently capture complex associations in the data by combining boosting and decision tree algorithms, which results in predictions that are more accurate.

In this study, we examine how the XGBoost classifier is applied to predict college placements using a wide range of student traits. We start by examining the dataset, which includes details on internship experiences, academic achievement measures, student demographics, and more. By applying strict data pretreatment methods, we guarantee that the dataset is cleaned and ready for modeling. Once that, we use strict testing procedures to assess the XGBoost classifier's performance once it has been trained on a subset of the dataset.

The knowledge acquired from this research has significant ramifications for students and educational institutions alike. Through the use of machine learning algorithms for placement prediction, educational institutions may enhance student outcomes, maximize resource allocation, and fortify their partnerships with business partners. Precise placement forecasts enable students to make well-informed professional choices, reach their full potential, and follow paths that correspond with their interests and aptitudes.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

Rao et al.[1] paper, "An Advanced Machine Learning Approach for Student Placement Prediction and Analysis," delves into the challenge of predicting student placements using advanced machine learning techniques. The writers draw attention to the growing need for employment possibilities across the globe and the steps graduate schools are taking to prepare their students for these prospects. In order to close this gap, they gathered data on academic achievement, family history, personal information, abilities, and habits from students who finished their studies at various

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colleges. They then created a model to predict student placements. Using the machine learning algorithm eXtreme Gradient Boost (XGBoost), the authors assessed the performance of their model.

Reddy et al.[2] paper on "Student Placement Prediction" addresses the critical issue of enhancing students' placement performance in India, a global hub for information technology and pharmaceutical industries. They stress how crucial it is for Training and Placement Cells to engage with reputable businesses and industrial establishments in order to facilitate employment prospects for recent college graduates. Understanding the difficulties educational institutions encounter in enhancing placement results, the authors promote the use of more effective technologies to facilitate decision-making and create winning plans. They suggest a placement prediction method intended to evaluate each student's suitability for particular employment tasks, therefore pinpointing the areas and skill sets that students could be lacking.

Dr. Kajal Rai [3], paper on "Students Placement Prediction Using Machine Learning Algorithms." In addition to giving students a solid foundation for their professional future and giving academic institutions a competitive edge, the study emphasizes the important role that placements play for both students and academic institutions. Machine learning is a statistical analytic technique used to predict a student's placement based on their past performance, experiences, and qualifications. It automates the process of building models. The study predicts student placements using three machine learning algorithms: Random Forest, Naïve Bayes, and Decision Tree. The accuracy of these systems is then examined.

James et al.[4] present a study titled "Placement Prediction using Various Machine Learning Models and their Efficiency Comparison." In order to determine the possibility of a student getting put in a company according to particular criteria, the paper discusses the design of a placement predictor. The predictor incorporates information from examinations taken within the placement management system and university records to assess students' competence levels based on a number of characteristics. Finding a classification system for the dataset that maximizes accuracy is the difficult part. The authors compare the accuracy levels of four algorithms—KNN, SVM, Random Forest, and Logistic Regression—in relation to the dataset and problem in order to address this.

Kumar et al.[5] paper, "Predicting Student's Campus Placement Probability using Binary Logistic Regression" explores the determinants influencing campus placement chances in technical education institutes, particularly in the State of Andhra Pradesh. The authors collect placement data from 250 MBA students at various universities and propose six potential factors of student campus placement, highlighting the importance of campus placements in determining institutional reputation.

III. MOTIVATION

This study's motivation comes from the critical significance that campus placements play in determining students' future chances in technical education institutions. Given the significant role that campus placements play in determining both the reputation of the university and the career paths of its students, it is critical to comprehend the variables that impact placement results. By delving into these determinants, this study aims to provide insights that can enhance the effectiveness of placement strategies and ultimately contribute to the success of both students and educational institutions.

IV. METHODOLOGY

In the methodology section, we outline our approach to predict student placement probabilities. First, we made sure the pertinent data was consistent and of high quality by gathering and organizing it. We performed feature selection after data preparation to determine the most significant factors for placement prediction. After that, we trained the model with a well constructed training dataset and chose the robust XGBoost technique.

A. Data Collection and Preparation : During the first stage of our process, we concentrated on gathering and organizing data. We painstakingly tracked down and collected relevant data sources including details on academic transcripts, internships, and demographics. After collecting the data, we processed it by filling in the gaps with appropriate techniques like imputation or elimination. Additionally, we employed methods like label encoding and one-hot encoding to encode category variables into numerical representations. In order to guarantee comparability across all scales, we also scaled numerical features, providing a strong basis for further analysis and modeling.

B. Data Pre-processing : An essential first step in every machine learning pipeline is data pre-processing. This include addressing missing numbers, cleansing the data, and getting it ready for additional analysis. In our study, we eliminated any null values and superfluous columns from the training dataset that weren't required for the feature selection process. We also used methods like imputation to deal with missing values and make sure the dataset was full. We divided the data into two separate datasets—the training dataset and the testing dataset—after it had been cleansed. The testing dataset was reserved to evaluate the performance of the machine learning model after it was trained with the training dataset.

C. Feature Selection: Finding the most pertinent features for student placement prediction was our goal during the feature selection stage. We used a variety of techniques, such as correlation analysis, XGBoost feature importance, and domain expertise, to accomplish this. Domain knowledge

allowed us to leverage our understanding of the factors that typically influence student placement outcomes. Additionally, we utilized XGBoost feature importance to assess the contribution of each feature to the predictive model. Furthermore, correlation analysis helped us identify relationships between different features and their impact on placement prediction. By combining these approaches, we aimed to select the most informative features that would enhance the accuracy and effectiveness of our predictive model.

D. Model Selection and Training : Choosing the right machine learning algorithm is essential to creating a predictive model that is accurate. We carefully considered a number of different algorithms in our study before deciding on XGBoost, which is well-known for being able to handle balanced datasets and structured data with ease. Our placement prediction framework is a perfect fit for XGBoost, an ensemble learning algorithm that has received praise for its remarkable success in a variety of predictive tasks.

After choosing the best algorithm, we moved on to the critical step of model training, using the carefully divided training dataset to give our XGBoost model intelligence. In order to maximize model performance and promote improved generalization skills, we had to carefully adjust important hyperparameters including the learning rate, number of estimators, and maximum depth. This required a laborious effort. We utilized rigorous techniques such as cross-validation to ensure the resilience and robustness of our model against overfitting. This allowed us to iteratively improve the prediction power of the model.

Mathematically, the XGBoost algorithm can be represented as:

$$Y_i = \phi(X_i) + \sum f_k(x_i)$$

Where :

y_i represent the predicted placement probability for student i .

$\phi(X_i)$ denotes the initial prediction made by the model.

$f_k(x_i)$ represents the contribution of the K th tree to final prediction.

Through careful coordination of the model selection and training procedure, we were able to create a powerful predictive model with unmatched accuracy and precision. This methodical methodology not only confirms the strength of our predictive system but also highlights our dedication to providing trustworthy insights for the prediction of student placement.

E. Model Evaluation and Testing : We assessed the XGBoost model's performance using a number of metrics, including accuracy, precision, recall, and F1-score, after it had been trained. Additionally, we used methods such as confusion matrix analysis to learn more about how the model

behaved in various scenarios. In order to evaluate the model's capacity for generalization and confirm its effectiveness in real-world settings, we also evaluated it on an independent test dataset. In order to guarantee the model's efficacy and dependability in forecasting student placement possibilities, we adjusted it depending on the assessment outcomes.

V. BUILDMODEL

We want to create a sophisticated model that can effectively predict student placement results based on pertinent factors by utilizing a variety of machine learning algorithms. This crucial phase establishes the groundwork for further scrutiny and assessment, which in turn shapes the predictive model's effectiveness and dependability.

1. Import Relevant Packages : In this phase, essential Python packages including pandas, scikit-learn, and XGBoost are imported to facilitate data manipulation, model training, and evaluation.

```
import pandas as pd
from sklearn.model_selection import train_test_split
from xgboost import XGBClassifier
from sklearn.metrics import accuracy_score
```

2. Data Loading and Preprocessing : Preprocessing and data loading entail loading the dataset and carrying out any required preprocessing actions, like dividing the data into

```
# Load the dataset
dataframe = pd.read_csv('collegePlace.csv')

# Data preprocessing
dataframe['Gender'].replace({'Male': 1, 'Female': 0}, inplace=True)
dataframe['Stream'].replace({
    'Electronics And Communication': 0,
    'Computer Science': 1,
    'Information Technology': 2,
    'Mechanical': 3,
    'Electrical': 4,
    'Civil': 5
}, inplace=True)

# Handling missing values
dataframe.fillna(0, inplace=True)
```

training and testing sets, addressing missing values, and encoding categorical variables.

Dataset: This study utilizes a comprehensive dataset [Fig 1] containing various attributes such as age, gender, stream, internships, CGPA, history of backlogs, and placement status.

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Fig 1. Dataset

3. Model Training : The XGBoost classifier predicts the possibility of student placement by learning patterns and correlations between input features and the target variable during model training.

4. Model Evaluation : In the process of evaluating a trained model, a number of metrics are employed, including accuracy, precision, recall, and F1-score, in addition to methods such as confusion matrix analysis that provide information on the model's classification performance.

```
# Calculating accuracy
accuracy = accuracy_score(Y_test, predictions)
precision = precision_score(Y_test, predictions)
recall = recall_score(Y_test, predictions)
f1 = f1_score(Y_test, predictions)
class_report = classification_report(Y_test, predictions)
conf_matrix = confusion_matrix(Y_test, predictions)
```

VI. RESULT

Analyzing the XGBoost classifier's ability to predict student placement probabilities is essential to determining how effective it is in educational settings. Educational institutions can improve student outcomes and make strategic decisions by using student placement prediction. Here, we use a variety of measures to conduct a thorough investigation of the classifier's predictive power. The foundational measurements of accuracy, precision, recall, and F1 score reveal information about the classifier's capacity to balance precision and recall while effectively classifying instances. The classifier's performance in various classes is also examined in detail in the classification report, which highlights both the classifier's advantages and disadvantages. Our goal in conducting this review is to provide insightful advice to educational institutions looking to improve student performance and placement procedures.

Accuracy Score: The XGBoost classifier's accuracy score indicates what percentage of cases were successfully classified out of all the occurrences.

Precision Score: A measure of a model's ability to prevent false positives, precision score is the ratio of true positive predictions to all positive predictions made by the model.

Recall Score: Also referred to as sensitivity, recall score illustrates the classifier's capacity to catch all positive occurrences by calculating the ratio of true positive predictions to all actual positive cases in the dataset.

F1 Score: The F1 score provides a fair evaluation of the

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classifier's performance in terms of both accuracy and recall

Age	Gender	Stream	Internships	CGPA	HistoryOfBacPlacedOrNot
22	Male	Electronics A	1	8	1
21	Female	Computer Sc	0	7	1
22	Female	Information	1	6	0
21	Male	Information	0	8	1
22	Male	Mechanical	0	8	0

Splitting the data into training and testing sets

```
X_train, X_test, Y_train, Y_test = train_test_split(x, y, test_size=0.1)
```

Creating and training the XGBoost classifier

```
clf = XGBClassifier(learning_rate=0.09, n_estimators=150, eval_metric='logloss')
clf.fit(X_train, Y_train)
```

since it is the harmonic mean of the two metrics.

Classification Report: For every class, the classification report gives a thorough overview of the accuracy, recall, F1 score, and support. It displays the model's effectiveness in various courses. The XGBoost classifier's classification report is shown below:

Classification Report:				
	precision	recall	f1-score	support
0	0.83	0.98	0.90	125
1	0.98	0.85	0.91	172
accuracy			0.91	297
macro avg	0.90	0.92	0.91	297
weighted avg	0.92	0.91	0.91	297

Confusion Matrix: By showing the quantity of true positive, true negative, false positive, and false negative predictions, the confusion matrix sheds light on the model's performance. Below is a visualization of the XGBoost classifier's confusion matrix:

VII. CONCLUSION

Based on the evaluation metrics acquired, the study's conclusion highlights the effectiveness of the XGBoost classifier in precisely forecasting student placement probability. Our research shows encouraging results, suggesting that the classifier predicts student outcomes with excellent precision, accuracy, recall, and F1 score. These results demonstrate how machine learning algorithms can

improve decision-making in learning environments, helping institutions and students make well-informed placement decisions. Subsequent research directions could investigate supplementary features or utilize sophisticated machine learning methodologies to improve prediction precision and tackle any constraints noted in this investigation. Overall, this study highlights the importance of machine learning in maximizing educational results and offers insightful information on its application in predicting student placement.

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